

Usage of Deep Learning in skin cancer detection

Automated diagnosis of melanomas through deep learning trained neural networks

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ABSTRACT

Image recognition is an important topic when it comes to skin cancer detection, since the incidence of skin cancer is rising sharply, worldwide, and the detection of pigmented lesions is still a challenge for dermatologists. The field constitutes an interface between dermatology and computer science and combines conventional detection methods with KI systems. Studies have shown that convolutional networks cause good outcomes in skin cancer detection due to its handling with big data, an AUC at 99% with a ResNet-152 was measured. The diagnostic accuracy is impressive and can be compared to a dermatologists decision. However, there are some limitations, e.g. restricted training data, that need to be considered and also further explored, therefore at the moment it can be only used as an assisting tool.

KEYWORDS

Data science, neural networks, early cancer detection, automatic melanoma classification, deep learning

1 INTRODUCTION

The incidence of skin cancer is rising sharply worldwide in most countries and with it also the incidence of melanomas, which are responsible for the majority of skin cancer mortality. But still, melanoma recognition also today is a major diagnostic challenge. [1]

Best healing chances for melanomas can be achieved when the skin lesion is diagnosed at an early stage. Through the challenge to diagnose this kind of skin cancer the mortality is very high, for example in 2016 3,000 out of 23,000 patients died with this diagnosis. [2]

2 BACKGROUND

Automated recognition of pigmented skin lesions, in particular diagnosis of melanomas, constitutes an interface between dermatology and computer science, though these fields analyze from different perspectives. On the dermatology's side are mostly clinical studies where KI systems are tested on probands and

compared to the assessment of a dermatologist and on the computer science's side there are mostly publications about the technical background of the melanoma recognition algorithms. [3]

3 METHODS

3.1 ABCDE method

Lay diagnostics work with the ABCDE method, which stands for asymmetry, border, color, diameter and evolving of a skin alteration. The concentration of the macroscopic evaluation should lie on those lesions which differ from the other skin alterations of one patient. The origin name of this comparing method was the "ugly duckling sign". [4]

With this method the dermatologist increases the diagnostic accuracy for melanoma detection, by adding the dermatoscopy. In the recent decades, automated systems for image assessment in dermatology have been increasingly developed and tested in studies, two of them the algorithm by Menzies et al. and Argenziano et al., which can be used for dermatoscopic evaluation. [5, 6]

3.2 Scheme for early automated diagnostic systems

Most automated diagnostic systems underlie a specific and standardized workflow, which is divided into four steps:

- Preprocessing
- Segmentation
- Feature Extraction
- Classification [7]

Preprocessing: This step takes care of a trouble-free process of the algorithm - it standardizes the starting situation before the actual analysis begins. The preprocessing includes eliminating disturbing elements of a picture ("artifact rejection") and improvement of the picture ("image enhancement"). One of the most common and important rejections is the removal of hair in one shot, where the pixels with hair are being replaced with surrounding pixels. [8]

Segmentation: The segmentation step defines the ROI ("region of interest") of one picture. This step separates this region from the

rest of the picture, which creates a binary mask. There are several common methods for segmentation, e.g.: “thresholding methods” (brightness, light as factor for segmentation), “edge-based methods” (change of characteristics in one picture), “region-based methods” (assumption that it contains two areas: lesion and background, which are the two regions in a picture). [9]

Feature Extraction: In this step the features are extracted, which can be used for classification. These features are derived from the characteristics, which are also used for diagnostics by a dermatologist, for example for the ABCDE method. These assessments need to be measurable to be analyzed by an algorithm. In an automated diagnostic system mostly only the ABCD features are used, since the “E” can only be significant when the lesion was measured repeatedly. [10]

The features are always rated and for the classification are only the most significant features chosen, which don’t necessarily have to be the ABCD features, but sometimes others or only some of them.

Classification: The last step towards a diagnosis constitutes the classification, which is binary (melanoma/nevus or suspicion of melanoma/definitely benign). The most common classification methods are the following:

- “Support vector machines”: They arrange the learned lessons from the training in a way that the to distinguish classes can be completely separated from each other by a hyperplane. This way different lesions are as far away from the hyperplane as possible.
- “K-nearest neighbors”: The classification of one lesion is made by the class of the most similar lesion (nearest neighbor) with a known and correct diagnosis. The most often used class of the neighbors is chosen with the kNN method.
- “Ensemble classifier”: This method combines different classification methods to get better results.
- “Decision Trees”: According to the characteristics the lesions are divided into smaller groups which are assigned to a class.
- “Bayesian classifier”: With this method the probabilities for each class are calculated. [11]
- “Artificial neural networks”: ANN’s process information in multi-layered, interconnected units. They probably have relatively little in common with biological neural networks due to limited knowledge of the human cognitive apparatus. Classes are calculated by algorithms that minimize the sum of classification errors. The classification of lesions is learned by the system itself through the presentation of large amounts of data during the training and the formation of certain patterns. [12]

3.3 Deep learning trained neural networks

Today neural networks are trained by “deep learning”, these networks are oriented towards the structure of the human brain. Examples are GoogLeNet or ResNet, which classify to a great extent autonomously.

The structure of a network consists of various layers: The “Input” layer receives a picture, the “Output” layer puts out the result of the calculations. In addition to these two layers there are a various number of so-called “hidden-layers” which are responsible for the actual analysis of the picture.

Fig. 1: Deep neural network [16]: <https://www.ibm.com/cloud/learn/neural-networks>

The output is created by a Softmax-function which puts out a value between 0 and 1, which can be interpreted as the probability between 0 and 100 % for a specific diagnosis. An alternative represents the “content-based image retrieval” method, which matches the given lesion visual with a similar dermoscopic image of the training data with the associated diagnosis. [13]

Two different training methods are used in deep learning: supervised and unsupervised learning. While the supervised training learns from pictures with the assigned diagnoses it is the opposite with the unsupervised learning, here the neural network builds groups out of similar pictures without having diagnoses to the learning data.

Since classification methods perform best with more data Convolutional neural networks are in favor because of their complexity to work with big data. CNN’s are typically used for image classification since it can handle global data and also local data. For melanoma detection this is important because often in this field scientists do not have enough data from the dermatologists they work with so most studies have also therefore used transfer learning with accessible image databases. These databases are also co-responsible for the success of CNN’s in skin cancer detection.

4 STUDIES

A study from 2017, published by Esteva et al., let 21 dermatologists compete with an Inception V3, which is a Google based CNN. The training contained a basic training of 1.28 million objects and further training with 129,450 pictures of skin lesions. In 2018 a study by Haenssle et al. used an Inception V4 with the same basic training and then further training with 100,000 pictures of skin lesions. This study involved 58 dermatologists. In both studies the

dermatologists lost against the algorithm, they were shown 100 pictures of nevi and melanomas. [14, 15]

Several other studies are also very promising to classify whether a skin lesion is benign or malignant, studies have shown the last years that overall CNN trained networks can classify at least as precise as dermatologists. Only very skilled experts in their field can be as good as, or in some cases better than, the algorithm.

The results of CNN's in skin cancer classification perform very good compared to other algorithms. There were outcomes of 85,5% accuracy in melanoma classification with Convolutional neural networks. When it comes to pretrained deep CNN'S the accuracy is even higher: A system of AlexNet, ResNet-18 and VGG16 with a multi-class SVM classifier could reach 97,55% and 83,83% AUC (area under the curve) in melanoma classification. [17] Also a pretrained ResNet-152 was tested for 12 different kinds of skin lesions, this system reached 99% AUC. [18]

Limitations are everywhere, where there is not so much training data. Archives that provide scientists with picture material for example don't have as many data of skin lesions in the fingernail area and mucous membrane. Also, a different skin color is an important issue, not only for neural networks but also for dermatologists it is more difficult to get to the correct diagnosis with different appearances of the skin and lesions.

5 PROSPECT

Diagnostic systems are able to classify suspicious skin lesions correctly, the diagnostic accuracy is impressive, since the neural networks can be compared to experienced dermatologists. Although there are numerous of limitations to the technology and more important limitations that are not known of yet. It is essential to discover the unknown limitations to counteract and improve classification methods.

It is not conceivable to work without a dermatologist at this stage, but neural networks are already a helpful assistance tool for skin cancer detection. The most important question will be how humans and computer can work even better together in the future.

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